

THE POLICY OF LEARNER AUTONOMY AND THE LANGUAGE TEACHERS' TASK IN FOSTERING IT

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Abstract

Curriculum reform carried out in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan emphasizes learner autonomy. The role of teacher in guiding learners toward gaining learners autonomy stands out. The article gives information about learner autonomy and discusses significance of the role of the teacher in developing learner autonomy.

Keywords: learner autonomy, language learner, the role of the teacher, university students

Introduction

On October 8, 2019, the president of Uzbekistan signed the Decree "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". This policy document defines "to include at least 10 higher educational institutions of the republic in the list of higher educational institutions occupying the first 1,000 places in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Niger Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities) and gradually transfer the educational process in higher educational institutions to a credit-moodle system". This system is based on European Credit Transfer system, where emphasized the notion of learner autonomy. The concept of 'learner autonomy' existed in the syllabus of universities even before the introduction of the credit -moodle system, but only a limited number of educational institutions specifically focused on autonomous language learning. To date, all the universities of the Republic tasked with promoting and fostering learner autonomy, but as the author the teacher of Japanese language, this article will discuss the autonomy of language learner and some difficulties in putting the theory into practice.

Learner autonomy and approaches to foster it

Learner autonomy and its benefits in learning a foreign language has been discussed in the field of foreign language learning for many years. A large literature on autonomy in language learning now exists, with Holec (1981)

commonly cited as a seminal contribution to the field. Sinclair (2000) suggests 13 aspects of learner autonomy that are generally accepted by academics and researchers working in the field.

1. Autonomy is a construct of capacity
2. Autonomy involves a willingness on the part of the learner to take responsibility for their own learning
3. The capacity and willingness of learners to take such responsibility is not necessarily innate
4. Complete autonomy is an idealistic goal
5. There are degrees of autonomy
6. The degrees of autonomy are unstable and variable
7. Autonomy is not simply a matter of placing learners in situations where they have to be independent
8. Developing autonomy requires conscious awareness of the learning process-i.e. conscious reflection and decision-making
9. Promoting autonomy is not simply a matter of teaching strategies
10. Autonomy can take place both inside and outside the classroom
11. Autonomy has a social as well as individual dimension
12. The promotion of autonomy has political as well as psychological dimension
13. Autonomy is interpreted differently by different cultures

In order to succeed in fostering learner autonomy, based on a large number of existing studies, we (teachers of Japanese language of Uzbekistan) must work out approaches that will suit the mentality of our country's students. For example, Benson (2011) proposes six different approaches to developing autonomy which include resource-based approach (learners' independent interaction with learning materials), technology-based approach (computer assisted language learning), learner-based approach (behavioral and psychological changes in the learners), classroom-based approach (learners work with their peers and teachers in the classroom contexts), curriculum-based approach (emphasizes the idea of learner control over the curriculum as a whole), teacher-based approach (emphasizes the role of teachers and teachers' professional development for fostering autonomy in their learners).

The role of the teacher in developing learner autonomy

The contribution of learner autonomy to effective language learning is proved by a lot of studies. Little (1991), summarized the benefits of promoting learner autonomy in three areas: The first is that since learners participate in the

process of making decision, “learning should be more focused and more purposeful, and thus more effective both immediately and in the longer term” (Little, 1991;p.8). The second one is that “because responsibility for the learning process lies with the learner, the barriers between learning and living that are often found in traditional teacher-led educational structures should not arise” (Little,1991). And the third benefit is that learners transfer this autonomy to other areas of their lives, and this makes them more responsible people in the society. There are some other experts in the field that have found some evidence about learner autonomy’s effectiveness; Dam and Legenhausen (1996), Benson (2008), Litttwood (1997) etc. Thus autonomy improves the quality of language learning, promotes democratic societies, prepares individuals for life-long learning, that it is a human right, and that it allows learners to make best use of learning opportunities in and out of the classroom.

Autonomy in learning a foreign language is perceptibly crucial. Speaking about the current methods of teaching the Japanese language, it is worth noting here that teacher-centered education is still practiced in Uzbekistan. Yumi Abe dispatched by JICA to Uzbekistan to University of World Languages from 2018 to2022 in her home page characterizes Japanese language students as ‘accustomed to passive-style classes’. She notes that along teaching Japanese language and literature, she is introducing new teaching methods to colleagues and taking on the challenge of collaborative practice. In order to boost the quality of language learning and shift Japanese learning students from passive learners to active learners, the traditional methods of learning should be replaced with the new methods which are more effective.

The role of teacher in guiding learners toward gaining learners autonomy is indisputable. To promote autonomy in language learning a teacher must have necessary skills with regard to learner autonomy first. Autonomy, in order to be strengthened, needs to be mutual; meaning that not only students, but also teachers should understand and facilitate it (Kashefian,S. , Kouhpeyma, Y.2020;p.198). According to Borg (2011) teachers’ beliefs can powerfully shape both what teachers do and, consequently, the learning opportunities learners receive.

Conclusion

This paper accentuates significance of learner autonomy and introduces current situation of Japanese language teaching of Uzbekistan. As we have seen, Japanese teachers of Uzbekistan have the goal of introducing, promoting and fostering learner autonomy in their classes. We are witnessing here the early

stage of the process. To achieve the desired results, we must first of all scrutinize existing studies related to different areas of learner autonomy, and work out strategies, which will be relevant to our Uzbek cultural context, because teacher education is more likely to have an impact on teachers' practices.

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